

AAE59000MAAC Week 11 reading report

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Abstract—This paper gives a selective overview of multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) with an emphasis on algorithms that admit theoretical guarantees. Instead of treating MARL as only a collection of empirical methods, the authors organize the literature through two main mathematical frameworks, namely Markov/stochastic games and extensive-form games, and review theory-oriented methods for cooperative, competitive, and mixed settings. The paper is especially valuable because it clarifies the main structural difficulties in MARL, including non-stationarity, scalability, equilibrium selection, and information constraints, while also identifying directions where rigorous analysis is still limited.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Reinforcement learning has achieved strong results in sequential decision-making problems, but many real systems involve several decision makers interacting in the same environment. Once multiple agents are present, the problem is no longer a standard single-agent Markov decision process. Each agent not only reacts to the environment, but also affects the environment experienced by the others through its own actions and policy updates. This leads naturally to the framework of multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL), which is relevant to robotics, autonomous driving, communication networks, cyber-physical systems, economics, and strategic games.

The main motivation of this paper is to review MARL from a theoretical point of view. In recent years, many empirical MARL algorithms have shown impressive performance, especially in large-scale games and simulation platforms. However, compared with single-agent RL, the theoretical understanding of MARL remains much more limited. The difficulty is not only computational. It is also conceptual: in multi-agent systems, the learning goal itself may not be unique, the environment becomes non-stationary when all agents learn simultaneously, the joint action space grows rapidly with the number of agents, and the available information may be decentralized or imperfect. Because of these issues, methods that work well in single-agent RL often do not transfer directly.

A second motivation of the paper is to organize the MARL literature in a clean mathematical way. Rather than giving a broad empirical survey, the authors focus on two formal models that support rigorous analysis: Markov/stochastic games and extensive-form games. These two frameworks cover a large part of the classical MARL theory. Within them, the paper further distinguishes fully cooperative, fully competitive, and mixed settings, since these interaction patterns lead to very different algorithmic ideas and convergence guarantees.

In my view, the paper fills an important gap. Many surveys describe what MARL algorithms exist, but this paper explains more clearly what is actually understood, what assumptions

are required, and where the main research gaps remain. In particular, it highlights areas such as decentralized MARL, partially observed settings, mean-field models, and policy-based learning dynamics, where the theory is still incomplete but highly relevant for practical systems.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The paper formulates MARL mainly through two frameworks: Markov/stochastic games and extensive-form games. These two formulations capture different types of interaction and information patterns.

A. Markov / Stochastic Games

A discounted Markov game can be written as

$$\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{S}, \{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}, P, \{R_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}, \gamma),$$

where

- $\mathcal{N} = \{1, \dots, N\}$ is the set of agents,
- \mathcal{S} is the state space,
- \mathcal{A}_i is the action space of agent i ,
- $P(\cdot | s, a)$ is the state transition probability under state s and joint action $a = (a_1, \dots, a_N)$,
- $R_i(s, a, s')$ is the one-stage reward function of agent i ,
- $\gamma \in [0, 1)$ is the discount factor.

At each time step t , the system is at state $s_t \in \mathcal{S}$. Each agent i selects an action $a_t^i \in \mathcal{A}_i$ according to its policy $\pi_i(\cdot | s_t)$. The joint action is denoted by

$$a_t = (a_t^1, \dots, a_t^N),$$

and the next state is generated according to

$$s_{t+1} \sim P(\cdot | s_t, a_t).$$

The discounted value function of agent i under joint policy $\pi = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_N)$ is

$$V_i^\pi(s) = \mathbb{E}_\pi \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t R_i(s_t, a_t, s_{t+1}) \mid s_0 = s \right].$$

A key difference from single-agent RL is that the return of agent i depends not only on its own policy π_i , but also on the policies of the other agents, denoted by π_{-i} . Therefore, the notion of an optimal policy is typically replaced by an equilibrium concept. A joint policy $\pi^* = (\pi_1^*, \dots, \pi_N^*)$ is a Nash equilibrium if, for every agent i ,

$$V_i^{\pi_i^*, \pi_{-i}^*}(s) \geq V_i^{\pi_i, \pi_{-i}^*}(s), \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall \pi_i.$$

That is, no agent can improve its expected discounted return by changing its own policy alone.

The paper divides Markov games into three main classes:

- **Fully cooperative:** all agents share the same reward function,

$$R_1 = R_2 = \dots = R_N.$$

- **Fully competitive:** typically the two-player zero-sum case, where

$$R_1 + R_2 = 0.$$

- **Mixed / general-sum:** the reward functions are neither identical nor exactly opposed.

These three settings require different solution concepts and different learning algorithms.

B. Extensive-Form Games

To model imperfect-information problems, the paper also uses extensive-form games. This framework is based on histories rather than only instantaneous states. An extensive-form game can be represented by

$$(\mathcal{N} \cup \{c\}, \mathcal{H}, \mathcal{Z}, \mathcal{A}, \{R_i\}_{i \in \mathcal{N}}, \tau, \pi_c, \mathcal{I}),$$

where

- \mathcal{H} is the set of histories,
- $\mathcal{Z} \subseteq \mathcal{H}$ is the set of terminal histories,
- \mathcal{A} is the action mapping,
- τ specifies whose turn it is to act,
- c denotes the chance player,
- π_c is the chance policy,
- \mathcal{I} is the collection of information states (or information sets).

If two histories belong to the same information set, the acting agent cannot distinguish between them. This captures imperfect information and partial observability. For a joint behavioral policy π , let $\eta^\pi(h)$ denote the probability of reaching history h . Then the expected return of agent i is

$$R_i(\pi) = \sum_{z \in \mathcal{Z}} \eta^\pi(z) R_i(z).$$

In this framework, a common approximate solution concept is the ε -Nash equilibrium. A joint policy π^* is an ε -Nash equilibrium if

$$R_i(\pi_i^*, \pi_{-i}^*) \geq R_i(\pi_i, \pi_{-i}^*) - \varepsilon, \quad \forall i, \forall \pi_i.$$

This means no agent can improve its payoff by more than ε through unilateral deviation.

C. Core Difficulty of the Problem

The paper makes it clear that MARL is not simply a higher-dimensional version of single-agent RL. The difficulty comes from the interaction structure itself. More precisely, there are several fundamental challenges:

- 1) the learning objective is not always unique;
- 2) each agent faces a non-stationary environment because the other agents are learning at the same time;
- 3) the joint action space scales combinatorially with the number of agents;
- 4) the available information may be local, delayed, or imperfect.

Therefore, the central problem studied in the paper can be summarized as follows:

Given a multi-agent sequential decision system with coupled dynamics, strategic interactions, and possibly decentralized or imperfect information, design learning algorithms that provably converge to an optimal cooperative policy or a meaningful equilibrium notion under reasonable computational and information assumptions.

III. MAIN RESULTS

Since this paper is a survey, its main contribution is not a single theorem, but a clear synthesis of the main theoretical ideas, algorithmic lines, and open difficulties in MARL.

A. Main Challenges in MARL

The first major result of the paper is its systematic explanation of why MARL is fundamentally harder than single-agent RL. One important point is that the learning goal itself can vary from problem to problem. In some settings, one aims for an optimal team policy; in others, one seeks a Nash equilibrium, correlated equilibrium, low-regret behavior, or some weaker form of stable strategic interaction. This means that even the notion of “success” is not universal in MARL.

The paper also emphasizes non-stationarity. In single-agent RL, the environment is usually modeled as fixed. In MARL, however, if each agent updates its policy over time, then from the viewpoint of any single agent the environment keeps changing. This breaks the stationarity assumption underlying many classical convergence arguments. As a result, methods that simply treat the other agents as part of the environment can be difficult to justify theoretically.

Another major challenge is scalability. If each of the N agents has action set \mathcal{A}_i , then the joint action space is

$$\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_1 \times \dots \times \mathcal{A}_N,$$

whose size is

$$|\mathcal{A}| = \prod_{i=1}^N |\mathcal{A}_i|.$$

This growth is exponential in the number of agents if the local action spaces have comparable size. Because of this, straightforward extensions of value iteration or Q-learning quickly become impractical.

Finally, the information structure has a decisive role. It matters whether training is centralized or decentralized, whether communication is available, and whether agents can observe the full state or only local signals. In many cases, theoretical guarantees become much easier in centralized settings and much harder in decentralized ones.

B. Algorithms for Cooperative MARL

For fully cooperative MARL, the team objective is aligned, so one may hope to adapt single-agent dynamic programming ideas. In the simplest case, if all agents share the same reward, then the system can sometimes be viewed as one large decision

maker acting in a joint action space. This viewpoint supports value-based methods and Q-learning-type algorithms.

However, the paper points out an important subtlety: convergence of value estimates does not automatically imply convergence of the agents' joint behavior. Even if the optimal value function is learned correctly, agents may still face a coordination problem when multiple equilibrium policies exist. In other words, agreement on values does not always guarantee agreement on policy selection.

The paper also reviews decentralized cooperative MARL, where agents learn locally and exchange information over a communication graph. This is especially interesting from a control and multi-agent systems perspective. Let the communication graph be

$$\mathcal{G}_c = (\mathcal{N}, \mathcal{E}),$$

where $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$ means that agents i and j can communicate. A typical decentralized update contains both a local temporal-difference term and a consensus term. At an abstract level, one may write

$$Q_i^{t+1} = Q_i^t + \alpha_t [\text{local Bellman update}] + \beta_t \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} (Q_j^t - Q_i^t),$$

where \mathcal{N}_i is the neighbor set of agent i . The first part updates the local value estimate using new data, and the second part pushes neighboring estimates toward consensus. This type of structure is one of the clearest links between MARL and distributed optimization or consensus theory.

C. Algorithms for Competitive MARL

The theoretical picture is stronger in fully competitive settings, especially in two-player zero-sum games. In this case, equilibrium analysis is cleaner because the interests of the two players are exactly opposed. For a zero-sum Markov game, if player 1 maximizes reward and player 2 minimizes it, one naturally arrives at a minimax value formulation of the form

$$V(s) = \max_{\pi_1} \min_{\pi_2} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r(s_t, a_t^1, a_t^2, s_{t+1}) \mid s_0 = s \right].$$

This structure makes it possible to develop Bellman-type operators, minimax Q-learning, and policy-gradient or actor-critic methods with saddle-point interpretations.

For extensive-form zero-sum games, the paper reviews important ideas such as fictitious play and counterfactual regret minimization (CFR). These methods are particularly suitable for imperfect-information games like poker. One useful perspective is that regret minimization can provide an alternative route to equilibrium computation, and some modern policy-based methods can be connected to this regret-based viewpoint.

D. Mixed / General-Sum Settings

The paper is more cautious in the general-sum case. These models are more realistic for many engineering and economic applications, but their theory is much less complete. In general-sum games, stationary Nash equilibria may exist, but learning dynamics do not necessarily converge to them.

Cycles, instability, and equilibrium selection issues become much more serious. Because of this, mixed settings remain one of the least understood parts of MARL theory.

This is an important message of the paper. The hardest problems are often the most realistic ones. Cooperative models are easier because all agents share a goal; zero-sum models are easier because there is a clean minimax structure; general-sum models are difficult because they contain strategic interaction without either of these simplifying properties.

E. My Understanding of the Key Idea

In my opinion, the most important idea of the paper is that MARL should be studied through several interacting layers:

- the **interaction structure** tells us whether the problem is cooperative, competitive, or mixed;
- the **information structure** determines what each agent can observe or communicate;
- the **solution concept** determines what kind of convergence is meaningful;
- the **learning architecture** determines what algorithmic guarantees are possible.

Because of this, MARL cannot be understood by discussing algorithms alone. The right mathematical framework depends on what kind of multi-agent system is being modeled. This is why the paper is useful: it organizes the theory in a way that makes these structural distinctions explicit.

IV. YOUR THOUGHTS ON FURTHER RESEARCH

This paper is highly relevant for future work on multi-agent coordination problems because it suggests that the first step is not to choose an algorithm, but to identify the correct interaction and information structure of the system.

One research direction that seems especially promising is decentralized cooperative MARL over communication networks. In many practical systems, there is no permanent central controller at execution time. Each agent has only local observations and communicates with a small subset of neighbors. This means that the purely centralized model is often too idealized. A more realistic formulation would combine local reward or value updates with graph-based information exchange, as in consensus-type learning rules.

A natural research question is how the communication topology affects learning performance. Suppose the agents communicate through an undirected graph with Laplacian matrix L . Then one may expect the algebraic connectivity of the graph, namely the second-smallest eigenvalue $\lambda_2(L)$, to influence how quickly information mixes through the network. This suggests a useful line of study: relate graph connectivity to the convergence speed and robustness of decentralized MARL algorithms. Such a direction would connect reinforcement learning with graph theory and multi-agent control in a mathematically meaningful way.

A second direction is to model partial information more carefully. In many real systems, an agent does not observe the full global state, and sometimes it cannot even infer the exact actions or policies of the other agents. The paper's distinction between Markov games and extensive-form games suggests

a gradual research strategy: start with a Markov-game model for analytical tractability, then introduce partial observability or hidden information step by step. This would allow the model to become more realistic without losing the possibility of rigorous analysis immediately.

Another important lesson from the paper is that convergence by itself is not enough. In engineering applications, we should also care about what the agents converge to, how much communication is required, and whether the final learning rule is implementable in a decentralized way. Therefore, future work should evaluate not only asymptotic convergence, but also coordination cost, communication burden, and robustness to imperfect information.

For a concrete next step, I think a good project would be the following. Consider a team of agents connected by a sparse communication graph. Each agent maintains a local critic or local Q -estimate, updates it from local data, and periodically exchanges compressed information with neighbors. Then study how graph sparsity, communication frequency, and heterogeneity in local rewards affect the learning trajectory. Mathematically, this is appealing because it combines RL, game structure, and network dynamics. From an application point of view, it is also closer to real multi-agent autonomy systems than fully centralized learning.

Finally, the paper also makes it clear that deep MARL theory and partially observed MARL remain open areas. My view is that a sensible research program should begin with structured small-scale models where the communication and observability patterns are simple enough to analyze. Once the core mechanism is understood, one can move toward richer function approximation and more realistic deep-learning-based architectures. In this way, theory can still guide the design instead of being left completely behind by practice.

REFERENCES

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